

An efficient algorithm for fast block matching using unsupervised bayesian classifier with bootstrap gaussian expectation maximization algorithm

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Abstract In this paper, a two-step block matching approach for motion estimation is proposed. To reduce the complexity of the algorithm, the static and dynamic blocks are identified using the unsupervised Bayesian classifier and the Gaussian Expectation of Maximization algorithm, and the final position of the dynamic blocks is found using the bloc matching algorithm and the Star Diamond Pattern. Based on a comparison with existing methods, the proposed method can produce faster calculation with good PSNR values.

Key words Motion estimation, Block matching algorithm, Bootstrap Gaussian Expectation Maximization Algorithm, Unsupervised Bayesian Classifier.

1 Introduction

Advances in artificial intelligence and multimedia technologies present a critical need to have visual management systems or user-friendly tools to assist in information retrieval from digital multimedia databases. Therefore, motion is the most obvious and effective feature to provide global and local understanding as well as to describe the dynamic content within video sequences. The extraction of motion parameters from video sequences has been one of the key elements in a range of applications from computer video through popular video compression standards such as the HEVC [1]-[4]. Motion estimation is a core part of video coding algorithms, which can effectively eliminate temporal redundancies between successive video frames to obtain high coding efficiency. The block matching

algorithm (BMA) has proven to be very popular through its easy implementation. Therefore, there is a need for optimization of the search process. The conventional exhaustive search algorithm FS (full search) divides the current frame into blocks, and each block is searched for the best match within a search window in the reference image. For each block, a motion vector corresponding to that displacement is associated. This algorithm combines the best in each block displacement vector, but it is very complex; it is not ready for real-time applications [4] [5][6].

Therefore, many fast algorithms have been proposed, such as the Three Step Search (TSS) [7], New Three Step Search (NTSS) [8], Two Minimum Three-Step Search Algorithm [9], Four-Step Search (FSS) [10], Simple and Efficient Search (SES) [11], Diamond Search (DS) [12], Novel Octagon Cross Diamond Search (NOCDS) [13], Hexagon Diamond Search (HDS) [14], Star Diamond (SD) [15], and many others[16][17][18][19]. Generally, all these algorithms develop a set of strategies for reducing FS complexity while trying to maintain its quality. One critical problem for these search algorithms is that they often test many points in the search procedure to find zero motion vectors for stationary blocks. The solution given in [18] converges in rare cases to a local minimum position. Based on the analysis of the matching error in the center window in real-world image sequences, we see that the matching error decrease as the search moves toward the global error minimum position. And, the value of the matching error in the center of the search window for stationary blocks is smaller than that for dynamic blocks; in other words, the global minimum of stationary blocks is in the center of the search window. Hence, in this paper, we propose a new efficient Star Diamond using Bootstrap Gaussian Expectation Maximization Algorithm with Unsupervised Bayesian Classifier (SDBGEM). The SDBGEM is used to classify blocs of frames into (static and dynamic motion) and with that we can eliminate the stationary motion from the motion estimation ME process. Two search patterns are used to track and refine different motion types: a star pattern followed by a small diamond pattern. The proposed algorithm is implemented on various test videos and compared to well-known block matching algorithms such as NOCDS, HDS, DS, FSS, TSS, SES, SD, SDth and the FS algorithm. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we outline the unsupervised Bayesian classifier with Gaussian expectation of the maximization approach and block matching method. In section 3, we describe in more detail the proposed SDBGEM algorithm. Numerical experiments, the results and comparisons are presented in Section.4. Section 5 provides conclusions.

2. Related work

2.1 Block matching algorithm

The block matching algorithm (BMA) for motion estimation plays an important role in video coding. In a BM algorithm, the current frame in a video sequence is divided into blocks. For each block in the current frame, the best matching block is identified inside a region of the previous frame, scheduled to minimize the sum of absolute differences (SAD). Unfortunately, SAD evaluation is computationally expensive and represents the most consuming operation in the BMA process. Therefore, BMA motion estimation is proposed as an optimization problem, and the overview of some block matching motion estimation algorithms ranges from the very basic full search to the recent fast star diamond algorithm. A full search algorithm is not fit for real-time applications because of its unacceptable computational cost. Full search consumes up to 80% of the computational power of the encoder by exhaustively evaluating all possible candidate blocks with the search window (Fig. 1) [4]-[6]. Hence, BMA [7]-[18] matures a set of strategies for reducing FS complexity while preserving its quality. However, one critical problem for these search algorithms is that they often consume more

time by testing many points in the search procedure to find zero motion vectors for stationary blocks. The most common matching criterion used is the sum of absolute differences (SADs), defined as:

$$SAD(d_x, d_y) = \sum_{i=1}^T \sum_{j=1}^T |f_k(i, j) - f_{k-1}(i + d_x, j + d_y)| \quad (1)$$

Where block size is $T \times T = 16 \times 16$ pixels and search window has size ± 7 pixels. d_x and d_y are vector indices of horizontal and vertical directions of motion. $f_k(i, j)$ is intensity of pixel (i, j) of sequence frame k and $f_{k-1}(i + d_x, j + d_y)$ is intensity of pixel $(i + d_x, j + d_y)$ of a frame $(k-1)$. Selected vector corresponds to a smallest error $SAD(d_x, d_y)$ in search window with $-7 \leq d_x \leq 7$ and $-7 \leq d_y \leq 7$.

Fig. 1 TxT block size matching approach within a search window

2.2 Block classification using Unsupervised Bayesian Classifier with Gaussian Expectation of Maximization

In a few video applications (video telephony, video conferencing, etc.), small motion is present between successive frames. Therefore, large numbers of blocks in the current frame are the same as in the reference frame (static blocks). The full search algorithm (16×16 block size and 7×7 search window size) on various test video sequences containing slow, medium or fast motion activity has shown that more than 50% of blocks are statics[15]. Table 1 indicates and confirms the strong probability of static blocks (null motion vectors) contained in different motion activity test video sequences. The study of matching error values shows that the algorithm converges to the global minimum error in the search window (e.g., Fig 2), and the global minimum for the stationary block is in the center search window. Therefore, the static block value is much smaller than that of the moving blocks in the center search window (see Figures 2, 3 and 4). Hence, the Bootstrap Gaussian Expectation of Maximization BGEM with unsupervised Bayesian classifier is used to find the threshold Th value, which is used to track and eliminate the invalid block class (static blocks) earlier from motion estimation[20][21]. A large reduction in computational load is then expected.

The results shown in Table 1 were obtained using the full search algorithm with a 16×16 pixel block size and a ± 7 pixel search window. This study is a new metric to classify each sequence type using a vector of class proportions. Sequences with high proportions of zero motion are considered static sequences. (Note that Paris and the container have more than 60% static blocks).

Table 1: Results of Unsupervised Bayesian Classifier with Gaussian Expectation of Maximization approach

Sequences	vector of class means Mu		vector of class proportions P		vector of class variances V	
	Class 1 static	Class 2 dynamic	Class 1 static	Class 2 dynamic	Class 1 static	Class 2 dynamic
Bus	12.3835	32.5654	0.5421	0.4579	31.0160	211.1425
Coastguard	6.8671	12.4536	0.8450	0.1550	5.3737	23.0704
Football	9.1323	33.1803	0.6511	0.3489	4.7803	216.6226
Flower	1.7697	25.5215	0.3456	0.6544	1.9532	216.5941
Stefan	2.3978	27.6146	0.2753	0.7247	1.6388	205.1604
Foreman	3.3566	11.7595	0.6713	0.3287	3.4093	43.3224
Table tennis	2.0955	19.1705	0.6918	0.3082	1.0173	210.2117
News	2.3168	11.9942	0.8939	0.1061	1.9911	118.3237
Paris	1.8779	10.7078	0.6851	0.3149	1.1425	47.9296
Silent	1.0775	2.5087	0.5338	0.4662	0.2542	0.8100
Tempete	6.1354	18.9382	0.9380	0.0620	16.6612	108.7019
container	1.7035	4.6703	0.8603	0.1397	0.9872	5.3636

Fig. 2 The matching error for one block in the search window using SAD (block size of 16x16 pixels and search window size of ± 7 pixels for the first pair of frames of the "Paris" sequence.

Fig. 3 The matching error for each block in the search window center (static and moving blocks) using SAD, block size of 16x16 pixels, and search window size of ± 7 pixels for the first pair of frames of sequence "Paris".

Fig. 4 Motion fields for static and moving blocks for the first pair of frames of sequence "Paris" using SAD, block size of 16x16 pixels and search window size of ± 7 pixels.

From this statement, the BGEM is used to classify blocks into two classes (static and dynamic) using unsupervised Bayesian classifier of static blocks as thresholds to eliminate invalid blocks earlier in the search process. This early stop scheme is incorporated into the initial steps of the star-diamond (SD) algorithm to recognize static blocks and stop-motion search [15]. Using a suitable threshold value for static blocks greatly reduces computational complexity and improves the quality of the predicted image. Determination of the cluster

value is performed by calculating the sum absolute difference for each block in the center search window SAD (0, 0) using equation (1) and takes the average value of the static block obtained by expectation of maximization as a threshold value for prejudgment of stationary blocks. For each scene, a different threshold can be used to distinguish between static blocks and dynamic blocks.

A statistical study for all blocks using the BGEM algorithm with unsupervised Bayesian classifier is conducted to classify the blocks into two classes[20][21]. A corpus that contains sequences with resolution (352x 288) consisting of 150 images each is used [15]. The results are shown in Table 1. The BGEM algorithm was implemented as a generalization of the k-means algorithm. The main differences are:

Let $Y = \{Y_i, i \in S\}$ be the random field corresponding to observations (SAD values at the center of the search window between two frames), whose values are in $D = \{1 \dots d\}$ and $X = \{X_i, i \in S\}$ represent the field of labels (classes) of values in a finite set $L = \{c1 \dots cK\}$. However, the difficulty with classification is the estimation of the unobserved (hidden) achievement $X = x$ from the observation $Y = y$. The fundamental assumption is that for any x configuration of X , random variables Y_i are conditionally independent:

$$P(y|x) = \prod_{i \in S} P(y_i|x_i) \quad (1)$$

The estimated classification image according to the maximum a posteriori (MAP) criterion is:

$$\hat{x} = \arg \max_x P(y|x)P(x) = \arg \min_x U(x|y) \quad (2)$$

Where $U(x|y)$ is an energy function. The optimal solution for this MAP estimator is obtained in a recursive manner using the iterative conditional mode (ICM) algorithm [20][21]. Having a given configuration $X_i = \mathbb{N}$ and insertion in the case of a mixture Gaussian parameter $\theta_{\mathbb{N}} = \{\mu_{\mathbb{N}}, \sigma_{\mathbb{N}}^2\}$, the estimation step of the BGEM algorithm to calculate the probability is as follows:

$$P^{(t)}(\mathbb{N}|y_i) = \frac{f^{(t)}(y_i; \theta_{\mathbb{N}})P^{(t)}(l|x_{N_i})}{P(y_i)} \quad (3)$$

Where $f^{(t)}$ is the Gaussian probability density function to iteration t of the BGEM algorithm and N_i is all the sites neighboring voxel i . In the BGEM, the probabilities are replaced by the local conditional probabilities:

$$P(\mathbb{N}|\hat{x}_{N_i}) = \frac{\exp(-U(\mathbb{N}|x_{N_i}))}{\sum_{\xi \in L} \exp(-U(\xi|x_{N_i}))} \quad (4)$$

To optimize the calculation time of BGEM, bootstrapping was introduced in the parameter estimation stage to estimate the parameter $\hat{\theta}_{\mathbb{N}}$ with B representative samples S_b ($b = 1 \dots B$) of the image. The parameters are updated by equations 3 and 4 and are performed on elements of the bootstrap sample \hat{y}_i^* . Indeed, the assumption of data independence is not considered only when estimating parameters by BGEM according to equation 1. However, it presents a necessary condition in the classification stage for energy minimization by the ICM (equation 2). The fully bootstrapped BGEM algorithm is described as follows:

On iteration (q);

At the iteration (t) of the ICM;

1. Withdrawal of a sample with a Size T_0 .
2. Sample Classification: Energy Minimizing using the Bootstrap sample as follows:

$$U(x|y) = \sum_{i \in S_b} \frac{(y_i^* - \mu_{x_i^*})^2}{2\sigma_{x_i^*}^2} + \log(\sigma_{x_i^*}) + \sum_{j \in N_i} \frac{\delta(x_i^*, x_j^*)}{d(i, j)} \quad (5)$$

y_i^* indicates an element of the bootstrap sample of class x_i^* ; note here that the labels used in this expression are for the current iteration.

3. Estimating parameters

$$\mu_i^{(b)} = \frac{\sum_{i \in S_b} P^{(t)}(l|y_i^*) y_i^*}{\sum_{i \in S_b} P^{(t)}(l|y_i^*)} \quad (6)$$

$$(\sigma_i^{(b)})^2 = \frac{\sum_{i \in S_b} P^{(t)}(l|y_i^*) (y_i^* - \mu_i^{(b)})^2}{\sum_{i \in S_b} P^{(t)}(l|y_i^*)} \quad (7)$$

- Repeat B iteration.
- Repeat until stabilization: the number of changes between iterations (t) and (t-1) is small.
- Repeat until the parameters converge.

This BGEN cycle is repeated for each new set of partitions until, as in the K-Means algorithm, the partition values no longer change by a significant amount.

Note that the threshold is determined between the first pair frames for each sequence and is then considered valid for all the sequences. For each sequence, we have a different threshold.

2.3 Search of dynamic blocks

In the proposed SDBGEM algorithm, two search patterns are employed (Figure 5). The shape of Fig. 5.a is called the star search pattern (SSP) and comprises nine checking points with eight points surrounding the center forming a star shape. The shape of Fig. 5.b is called the small diamond search pattern SDSP and has five check points.

Fig.5 Proposed SDBGEM algorithm search:

(a) Star search pattern (SSP) and (b) small diamond search pattern (SDSP).

3. Proposed algorithm

The proposed algorithm consists of two steps. In the first step of the Bootstrap Gaussian Expectation of Maximization approach (BGEM) with unsupervised Bayesian classifier is applied to determine the threshold value, and this threshold is used to eliminate static blocks from the motion estimation process.

In the second step, the Star Diamond algorithm is applied to estimate the final position of moving blocks [15](see Fig.6).

Proposed SDGEM search algorithm steps are:

Step 1: Compute SAD at the center point of the search window SAD (0,0).

If SAD (0, 0) is less than Th.

Block is stationary with Motion Vector (0, 0);

Else

Step 2: The Star Diamond Algorithm is employed to find the final motion vector (SAD_{min}) (using the coarse and fine search patterns of SD).

End.

Fig.6 Flow-chart of the proposed approach

4. Results and discussion

The algorithm was implemented and verified with various standard test video sequences, each having 150 frames of CIF format[15]. The reference, current and reconstructed frames for slow motion and fast motion video sequences are shown in Table 2. The performance of the FS, TSS, SES, FSS, NOCDS, HS, DS, SD, SDth and SDBGEM algorithms were compared in terms of the NPCavg [15] (Table 2) and the average PSNR (Table 3) for different standard test video sequences. The computational complexity is evaluated by NPCavg, and PSNR is shown confirmatively to assess whether video quality is maintained. For the SDBGEM algorithm, the obtained NPCavg values are low, and the PSNR values are the same for fast motion videos such as ‘Table Tennis’ and for slow motion videos such as ‘Paris’, as depicted in Tables 2 and 3. As one can verify by comparing the second and last columns of Table 3, the PSNR losses for the SDBGEM algorithm (relative to the FS algorithm) range from 0,35 dB (for ‘News’) to 0,41 dB (for ‘Table Tennis’). The optimality of the calculation of the threshold is given by the application of ‘Bayesian rule’ which is known by the minimization of the error probability. The Expectation of Maximization EM is a mixture identification algorithm and it prepares the Bayesian classifier. We also note that the threshold calculation is done automatically and adaptively to the data, a

Learning part by the EM is necessary. Real time is obtained by the Bootstrap process. And this is checked and confirmed by the results of Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2: NCPavg values for various search algorithms and sequences.

Sequences	FS	TSS	SES	FSS	NOCDS	HS	DS	SD	SD _{th}	SDBGEM
Bus	204.28	23.56	16.28	20.49	25.14	21.81	19.72	16.79	12.36	10.68
Coastguard	204.28	23.33	16.37	18.57	18.96	16.97	16.70	14.18	14.09	10.30
Stefan	204.28	23.31	16.40	18.68	20.05	17.50	17.05	14.97	11.72	9.45
Flower	204.28	23.31	16.09	18.39	20.26	16.99	15.90	13.94	9.68	9.81
Football	204.28	23.31	16.39	18.22	19.35	16.73	16.14	14.93	11.72	12.02
Foreman	204.28	23.29	16.28	18.13	19.38	16.29	15.76	14.05	11.50	8.73
Table tennis	204.28	23.30	16.60	17.33	16.12	13.99	14.47	13.63	9.14	6.71
News	204.28	23.21	16.96	16.19	13.37	11.35	12.83	12.54	1.98	3.15
Paris	204.28	23.21	16.94	16.20	13.36	11.51	12.83	12.56	5.05	5.04
Silent	204.28	23.21	16.89	16.37	13.73	11.82	13.14	12.90	3.85	7.82
Tempete	204.28	23.27	16.93	16.32	13.68	12.05	13.11	13.03	4.52	6.27
container	204.28	23.22	17.05	15.93	12.30	10.63	12.39	12.32	2.21	3.30

For NCPavg to measure the complexity of calculation, it is useful to define the complexity of an algorithm by the NCPavg considered as the average number of calculated points (NCP) on all blocks of the processed sequence (each sequence consists of 150 images).

The Number of Calculated Points (NCP) is defined by:

$$NCP = \frac{PxSAD}{mb} \quad (8)$$

Where:

P is the number total calculated SAD between two frames for all blocks to find all motion vectors.
SAD: Sum of Absolute Difference.

mb is the number of blocks on the devised frame into blocks with size $T \times T$.

It is clear that the complexity of the algorithm is much smaller than that of NCPavg.

Table 3: PSNR values for various search algorithms and sequences

Algorithms Sequences	FS	TSS	SES	FSS	NOCDS	HS	DS	SD	SD _{th}	SDBGEM
Bus	24.44	22.88	21.66	21.91	21.82	21.89	21.96	22.93	22.22	22.03
Coastguard	29.54	29.35	29.17	28.29	29.30	29.38	29.40	29.39	29.44	28.91
Stefan	24.96	24.61	23.95	24.13	23.93	24.08	24.10	24.54	24.38	22.82
Flower	25.80	25.33	25.26	25.57	25.70	25.73	25.76	25.71	25.76	25.78
Football	23.35	22.92	22.31	22.91	22.94	22.89	22.90	22.98	22.87	24.38
Foreman	32.89	32.39	31.98	32.52	32.40	32.25	32.66	32.46	32.55	32.35
Tabletennis	30.87	30.20	29.60	30.39	30.41	30.30	30.37	30.55	30.45	30.46
News	35.56	35.36	35.04	35.30	35.33	35.31	35.34	35.28	35.11	35.21
Paris	30.28	30.10	29.85	30.09	30.12	30.10	30.13	30.08	30.14	30.15
Silent	34.91	34.72	34.32	34.64	34.61	34.58	34.59	34.71	34.59	34.61
Tempete	26.47	26.39	26.28	26.31	26.31	26.31	26.30	26.28	26.24	26.30
Container	38.15	38.15	38.14	38.14	38.14	38.14	38.14	38.14	38.14	38.15

5. Conclusion

In this paper, a new method for motion estimation in video sequences is proposed based on the unsupervised Bayesian classifier with BGEM algorithm in the stage of the decision of dynamic or non dynamic block. It avoids any preprocessing procedure and improves the rate of classification of the statics, medium and speed motion vectors. Experimental results on a video data basis show that the proposed Star Diamond Search algorithm based on the BGEM algorithm with two steps proceeds motion estimation faster. Based on a comparative study, for the same quality reconstructed image, we have proven that the proposed method reduces the number of calculated points per block relative to the FS, TSS, SES, FSS, NOCDS, HS, DS, SD and SD_{th} algorithms. As future work we can use this method in video surveillance, moving object detection and tracking. The limitation of this method is that get the same results to others methods when the sequence content speed motion.

Ethics declarations

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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